

QUALITY OF LIFE IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE AND ERECTILE DYSFUNCTION ON RENAL REPLACEMENT THERAPY

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Abstract. To evaluate the impact of renal replacement therapy (RRT) on erectile function (EF) and quality of life (QoL) in patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD). A prospective observational study included 201 men with CKD who presented to a urology center with complaints of erectile dysfunction (ED). EF was assessed using the IIEF-5 questionnaire, and QoL was measured with the KDQOL-SF questionnaire at three time points: baseline, during severe azotemia, and after 12 months of hemodialysis. Statistical analysis was performed using ANOVA ($p < 0.05$). A progressive deterioration of EF was observed: the baseline IIEF-5 score was 21.9 ± 0.1 (62.7% without ED), during azotemia it dropped to 13.7 ± 0.1 (92.5% with mild-to-moderate ED), and after 12 months of hemodialysis — to 9.7 ± 0.1 (13.9% severe ED, 65.7% moderate ED, $p < 0.001$). QoL declined across all KDQOL-SF domains: “Symptoms/Problems” from 74.3 ± 0.8 to 60.1 ± 1.1 , “Sexual Function” from 83.5 ± 1.1 to 69.2 ± 0.8 , “Emotional Well-being” from 63.1 ± 1 to 50.1 ± 0.7 , and “Physical Functioning” from 64.2 ± 1.5 to 50.3 ± 1.2 ($p < 0.001$). CKD and hemodialysis significantly impair erectile function and quality of life, exacerbating physical, psycho-emotional, and social limitations.

Keywords: chronic kidney disease, hemodialysis, erectile dysfunction, quality of life.

Introduction. Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a progressive condition that impairs the physical, emotional, and social well-being of patients. Special attention is given to the quality of life (QoL) of patients at the end-stage of CKD who are receiving renal replacement therapy (RRT), including hemodialysis (HD), peritoneal dialysis, and kidney transplantation (KT). Alongside traditional clinical and laboratory indicators, increasing emphasis is being placed on patients' subjective assessments of their condition, including erectile function (EF).

According to the literature, QoL in patients on RRT improves significantly after kidney transplantation, especially in terms of physical activity, social adaptation, and psycho-emotional well-being [1]. At the same time, the introduction of modern dialysis methods (home HD, epoetin, active forms of vitamin D, calcimimetics) also positively influences QoL, making it comparable to that of kidney transplant recipients. It is also noted that patients' subjective perception of their condition may not coincide with the objective clinical picture, and therefore, QoL should be assessed using validated questionnaires [2]. Studies emphasize the importance of psychological and social rehabilitation as a key factor in restoring a full life for the patient [3]. Specialists recommend using psychometric scales and questionnaires to assess patients' attitudes toward their disease, including experiences related to erectile dysfunction (ED) [4].

Objective of the study. To evaluate the impact of CKD and RRT in the form of hemodialysis on EF and QoL of patients, and to identify key pathogenic mechanisms that impair sexual health and overall well-being.

Materials and Methods. The study was based on a prospective analysis of treatment outcomes in 201 male patients with CKD receiving RRT in the form of scheduled hemodialysis at the State Institution “Republican Specialized Scientific-Practical Medical Center of Urology” (Tashkent, Uzbekistan). The mean age of the patients was 35.2 ± 1.9 years. Most of the patients were young adults (18–44 years) — 80.6%. The proportion of middle-aged patients (45–59 years) was 18.9%, and elderly patients (60–74 years) made up only 0.5%. The primary cause of stage 5 CKD in most cases (87.6%) was chronic glomerulonephritis. Less common causes included polycystic kidney disease (3.0%), CKD of unknown etiology (3.0%), urolithiasis (2.5%), chronic pyelonephritis (2.0%), type 2 diabetes mellitus and congenital anomalies of the urinary tract (1.0% each).

The study complied with the Declaration of Helsinki, all patients provided informed consent, and the protocol was approved by the local ethics committee.

Inclusion criteria were: males with preserved EF, having a regular sexual partner, stable graft function, and no concomitant diseases in the exacerbation or decompensation stage.

In total, the study included the following observation stages:

- Initial stage – assessment of EF before the development of severe renal failure.
- Stage of severe azotemia – stage 5 CKD, characterized by the accumulation of uremic toxins and deterioration of systemic functions, including EF.
- 12 months after initiation of RRT – long-term assessment capturing the final impact of therapy on EF, including complete or partial EF recovery.

EF was assessed using the International Index of Erectile Function (IIEF-5) with the following classifications: severe ED (≤ 7), moderate (8–11), mild-to-moderate (12–16), mild (17–21), no ED (22–25). QoL was assessed using the KDQOL-SF questionnaire, which includes both specific (symptoms, impact and burden of kidney disease, work status) and general (physical and emotional functioning, social aspects) scales. Data were collected at each stage by surveying 76 patients from the sample using KDQOL-SF (the remaining 125 were not included in this analysis due to incomplete data). Statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS 26.0: a one-way ANOVA with Tukey's post-hoc test was applied for IIEF-5, and ANOVA was used for each KDQOL-SF scale. The significance level was set at $p < 0.05$. The study complied with the Declaration of Helsinki, patients gave informed consent, and the protocol was approved by the local ethics committee.

Results. At the initial stage of the study, 75 patients (37.3%) had mild ED, while 126 patients (62.7%) had no erectile dysfunction.

However, as CKD progressed to the terminal stage (stage 5 CKD) and during severe azotemia, all patients developed ED of varying severity — from mild to moderate (according to IIEF-5).

After 12 months of RRT (hemodialysis), no improvement in EF was observed. On the contrary, erectile dysfunction worsened in a significant portion of patients, and 13.9% were found to have severe ED (Table 1). These data underscore the importance of finding effective strategies for the correction and prevention of sexual dysfunction in CKD patients undergoing RRT.

At the initial stage (before the progression of azotemia), the average IIEF-5 index was 21.9 ± 0.1 , which indicates a significant decrease in EF, but still a preserved level of sexual activity.

At the stage of severe azotemia, further deterioration is observed — the IIEF-5 index decreased to 13.7 ± 0.1 , indicating a significant decline in erectile function (EF). One year after the

initiation of hemodialysis, an even more pronounced decrease in the index was noted, down to 9.7 ± 0.1 , which reflects a critical deterioration of EF despite ongoing renal replacement therapy.

A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) revealed a high level of statistical significance in differences between the observation stages ($F(2,600)=2418.29$; $p<0.001$), indicating a reliable decline in EF associated with CKD progression and the duration of hemodialysis.

Table 1.

Distribution of CKD Patients on Hemodialysis According to IIEF-5 Scores at Different Study Stages

ED Degree		Initial	High Azotemia Stage	12 months after initiation of RRT
Severe ED	n	0	0	28
	%	0.0%	0.0%	13.9%
Moderate	n	0	8	132
	%	0.0%	4.0%	65.7%
Moderate-mild	n	0	186	41
	%	0.0%	92.50%	20.4%
Mild	n	75	7	0
	%	37.3%	3.50%	0.0%
No ED	n	126	0	0
	%	62.7%	0.00%	0.0%
Total	n	201	201	201
	%	100%	100%	100%

The high prevalence of ED calls for regular screening and the implementation of treatment strategies for patients with CKD to improve their sexual health and overall quality of life. While the treatment of ED in CKD patients is essential, it is equally important to consider the broader impact of sexual health on mental well-being and interpersonal relationships, which may, in turn, affect treatment adherence and overall quality of life.

An analysis of the quality of life in patients with CKD and ED receiving RRT, based on the presented data from the KDQOL-SF questionnaire (an extended version of KDQOL-36 – Kidney Disease Quality of Life-36, a specialized tool for assessing QoL in CKD patients), demonstrates a progressive deterioration of quality of life over the 12-month course of RRT.

The data presented in Table 2 reflect the dynamics of quality-of-life indicators in CKD patients at different disease stages and over the course of one year of observation. The ANOVA revealed statistically significant differences across all scales ($p<0.001$). The most marked decline was recorded on the “Symptoms/Problems” scale ($F=54.63$), where scores dropped from 74.3 ± 0.8 to 60.1 ± 1.1 after 12 months, indicating a progressive worsening of patient condition. A substantial decrease was also observed on the “Effect of Kidney Disease on Daily Life” scale ($F=45.32$), with scores dropping from 71.4 ± 0.9 to 57.1 ± 1.2 after one year, pointing to increasing activity limitations.

On the “Burden of Kidney Disease” scale ($F=22.75$), a decrease from 38.2 ± 1.3 to 27.8 ± 1 reflects an increased perception of disease severity. The indicators of employment status also significantly worsened ($F=18.29$), dropping from 32.5 ± 1.5 to 21.9 ± 1.2 , which indicates a decline in patients’ ability to work (Table 2).

An analysis of the dynamics of psychosocial and functional components of quality of life in CKD patients on hemodialysis (Table 3) showed a statistically significant decline over time ($p < 0.001$). Cognitive function decreased from 85.1 ± 0.7 to 74.5 ± 1 points (a 12% decline), which may be associated with uremic intoxication and chronic hypoxia. The quality of social interaction worsened from 82.4 ± 0.8 to 68.1 ± 1.1 points (a 17% decline), reflecting increasing social isolation among patients undergoing long-term treatment. Erectile function scores dropped from 83.5 ± 1.1 to 69.2 ± 0.8 points (a 17% decline), confirming the significant impact of CKD on sexual health. Sleep quality declined from 59.3 ± 1.1 to 45.6 ± 0.8 points (a 23% decrease), indicating frequent sleep disturbances, which are typical for patients with end-stage CKD.

Table 2.

Specific components of quality of life according to the KDQOL-SF questionnaire related to kidney disease

Scale (number of items in the scale)	Initially (n=76)	High azotemia stage (n=76)	After 6 months (n=76)	After 12 months (n=76)	ANOVA F(3,300)	p
Symptoms/Problems (12)	74.3 ± 0.8	70.5 ± 0.9	65.2 ± 1	60.1 ± 1.1	54.63	< 0.001
Impact of Kidney Disease on Daily Activities (8)	71.4 ± 0.9	67.2 ± 1	62.3 ± 1.1	57.1 ± 1.2	45.32	< 0.001
Burden of Kidney Disease (4)	38.2 ± 1.3	35.1 ± 1.2	31.4 ± 1.1	27.8 ± 1	22.75	< 0.001
Employment Status (2)	32.5 ± 1.5	29.3 ± 1.4	25.6 ± 1.3	21.9 ± 1.2	18.29	< 0.001

Table 3.

Psychosocial and Functional Components of Quality of Life (KDQOL-SF) in CKD

Scale (number of items in the scale)	Initially (n=76)	High azotemia stage (n=76)	After 6 months (n=76)	After 12 months (n=76)	ANOVA F(3,300)	p
Cognitive functions (3)	85.1 ± 0.7	82.3 ± 0.8	78.4 ± 0.9	74.5 ± 1	39.92	< 0.001
Quality of social interaction (3)	82.4 ± 0.8	78.6 ± 0.9	73.2 ± 1	68.1 ± 1.1	55.49	< 0.001
Sexual functions (2)	83.5 ± 1.1	79.4 ± 1	74.1 ± 0.9	69.2 ± 0.8	53.51	< 0.001
Sleep (4)	59.3 ± 1.1	55.1 ± 1	50.2 ± 0.9	45.6 ± 0.8	48.94	< 0.001

An analysis of the dynamics of social and medical support indicators, as well as physical functioning in CKD patients, revealed a statistically significant decline over time ($p < 0.001$). Social support decreased from 71.2 ± 1.3 to 59.1 ± 1 points (a 17% decline), reflecting reduced involvement of family members and close relatives in patient care (Table 4). Support from dialysis staff worsened from 67.1 ± 1.1 to 55.4 ± 0.8 points (an 18% decline), which may indicate growing patient

dissatisfaction with the level of medical care. Satisfaction with medical care decreased from 51.4 ± 1.1 to 40.2 ± 0.8 points (a 22% decline), emphasizing the need to improve the organization of medical support for this patient population. Physical functioning declined from 64.2 ± 1.5 to 50.3 ± 1.2 points (a 22% decline), indicating progressively limited physical activity and reduced endurance.

Table 4.

Dynamics of Social and Medical Support Indicators, and Physical Functioning According to KDQOL-SF in CKD Patients on RRT

Scale (number of items in the scale)	Initially (n=76)	High azotemia stage (n=76)	After 6 months (n=76)	After 12 months (n=76)	ANOVA F(3,300)	p
Social support (2)	71.2±1.3	67.5±1.2	63.4±1.1	59.1±1	28.59	<0.001
Support of dialysis staff (2)	67.1±1.1	63.5±1	59.3±0.9	55.4±0.8	37.35	<0.001
Satisfaction with medical care (1)	51.4±1.1	48.1±1	44.3±0.9	40.2±0.8	34.42	<0.001
Physical functioning (10)	64.2±1.5	60.3±1.4	55.1±1.3	50.3±1.2	28.63	<0.001

An analysis of the dynamics of physical and emotional components of quality of life in CKD patients undergoing RRT (Table 5) revealed a statistically significant deterioration over time ($p < 0.001$).

Table 5.

Dynamics of Physical and Emotional Components of Quality of Life According to KDQOL-SF in CKD Patients on RRT

Scale (number of items in the scale)	Initially (n=76)	High azotemia stage (n=76)	After 6 months (n=76)	After 12 months (n=76)	ANOVA F(3,300)	p
Role limitations due to physical reasons (4)	37.4±1.4	33.1±1.3	28.6±1.2	24.3±1.1	28.34	<0.001
Pain (2)	61.3±1.4	57.4±1.3	52.7±1.2	47.9±1.1	29.94	<0.001
General health (5)	37.2±0.9	34.2±0.8	30.5±0.7	26.4±0.6	48.25	<0.001
Emotional well-being (5)	63.1±1	59.2±0.9	54.1±0.8	50.1±0.7	55.36	<0.001

Role limitations due to physical health declined from 37.4 ± 1.4 to 24.3 ± 1.1 points (a 35% decrease), indicating a significant impairment in patients' ability to perform daily duties. Pain levels increased, reflected by a drop in scores from 61.3 ± 1.4 to 47.9 ± 1.1 (a 22% decrease), highlighting increased discomfort and chronic pain. General health perception worsened from 37.2 ± 0.9 to 26.4 ± 0.6 points (a 29% decrease), indicating progressive deterioration in well-being and overall quality of life. Emotional well-being declined from 63.1 ± 1 to 50.1 ± 0.7 points (a 21% decrease), indicating a rise in anxiety, depression, and emotional exhaustion.

An analysis of the dynamics of psycho-emotional and socio-functional aspects of quality of life in CKD patients on RRT (Table 6) revealed a significant decline over time ($p < 0.001$). Role limitations due to emotional problems decreased from 74.2 ± 1.5 to 59.5 ± 1.2 points (a 20% reduction), indicating increasing emotional exhaustion and reduced motivation for daily activities. Social functioning dropped from 67.3 ± 1.2 to 53.7 ± 0.9 points (a 20% decrease), reflecting poorer social adaptation and reduced engagement in social life. Scores on the energy/fatigue scale decreased from 50.1 ± 1 to 37.2 ± 0.7 points (a 26% decline), indicating severe chronic fatigue, which is typical for patients with progressive CKD. Overall health perception declined from 49.2 ± 0.9 to 37.3 ± 0.6 points (a 24% decrease), confirming the growing perception of one's health as severe and limiting to daily life.

Table 6.

Psycho-Emotional and Socio-Functional Aspects of Quality of Life in CKD Patients on RRT

Scale (number of items in the scale)	Initially (n=76)	High azotemia stage (n=76)	After 6 months (n=76)	After 12 months (n=76)	ANOVA F(3,300)	P
Role limitations due to emotional reasons (3)	74.2 ± 1.5	70.1 ± 1.4	64.3 ± 1.3	59.5 ± 1.2	31.81	<0.001
Social functioning (2)	67.3 ± 1.2	63.2 ± 1.1	58.5 ± 1	53.7 ± 0.9	40.57	<0.001
Energy/fatigue (4)	50.1 ± 1	46.3 ± 0.9	41.7 ± 0.8	37.2 ± 0.7	53.39	<0.001
General health assessment (1)	49.2 ± 0.9	45.4 ± 0.8	41.2 ± 0.7	37.3 ± 0.6	56.81	<0.001

The most pronounced changes affected physical functioning (a 22% decline), role limitations due to physical health (35%), and chronic fatigue (26%), reflecting a deterioration in daily activity. Social functioning and support gradually weakened (a 17–20% decrease), intensifying patients' isolation. Cognitive function and emotional well-being also showed negative dynamics (12% and 21% declines, respectively), associated with uremic intoxication and psycho-emotional stress. A significant deterioration in sexual health (17%) highlights the need for its inclusion in a comprehensive rehabilitation approach for CKD patients. Overall, the progressive decline in all indicators emphasizes the need for enhanced medical, social, and psychological support for this patient group.

Discussion. This study revealed a significant deterioration in erectile function (EF) and quality of life (QoL) among patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD) on hemodialysis. Initially, 62.7% of patients had no erectile dysfunction (IIEF-5 = 21.9 ± 0.1), but during the stage of severe azotemia, ED developed in all patients (92.5% mild-to-moderate, 4.0% moderate; IIEF-5 = 13.7 ± 0.1), and after 12 months of hemodialysis, a further decline was observed down to 9.7 ± 0.1 (13.9% severe ED, 65.7% moderate, $p < 0.001$).

According to the study by Sánchez-González JC et al., which utilized the KDQOL-SF 36 questionnaire, patients receiving peritoneal dialysis reported higher subjective QoL scores compared to those on hemodialysis, especially in the domains of “mental health,” “general health perception,” and “illness-related stress” [5].

In a cohort study by Rincon Bello A. et al. involving 1,838 dialysis patients, it was found that higher scores on the HRQoL scale—particularly the physical and mental components and the Kidney Disease Summary Score—were significantly associated with lower risks of death and hospitalization during the one-year follow-up. Specifically, a 0.5 standard deviation increase in HRQoL was associated with a 7.4–11.4% reduction in mortality risk ($p < 0.05$), underscoring the prognostic significance of patients' subjective health assessments [6].

A systematic review by Chou J. et al. showed that up to 75% of men on hemodialysis suffer from ED, while the prevalence of sexual dysfunction among women ranges from 30–80%. The underlying causes include hormonal imbalances (low testosterone, hyperprolactinemia), anemia, psycho-emotional disorders (depression, anxiety), and the use of antihypertensive and antidepressant medications [7].

The study by Guerra V. et al. demonstrated that in men on hemodialysis, levels of albumin, hemoglobin, creatinine, and blood urea nitrogen correlated with EF ($p < 0.05$). Lower levels of these markers were associated with more severe manifestations of ED, suggesting their potential role as risk markers for sexual dysfunction [10].

In a study conducted by Wakeel J. et al. (Saudi Arabia), patients on peritoneal dialysis rated their overall and sexual health higher than patients on hemodialysis. The authors attribute this to greater autonomy, more flexible treatment schedules, and preservation of residual renal function with peritoneal dialysis [9].

The study by Dąbrowska-Bender M. et al. found that the presence of depression and anxiety significantly worsened QoL and sexual activity. Men with ED had high scores on the CES-D depression scale, which correlated with low sexual activity frequency and dissatisfaction with their sex lives [8].

Conclusion. The progression of CKD significantly reduces the quality of life in hemodialysis patients, affecting physical, emotional, cognitive, and social functioning. Physical limitations, chronic fatigue, ED, and reduced social activity are particularly pronounced. The data obtained highlight the need for comprehensive correction strategies, including hormonal, vascular, and psychosocial approaches, with a focus on restoring EF and emotional well-being.

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